

Heterosis for Seed Fibre Quality Traits Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Study of heterosis is very crucial to identify the promising hybrid combinations for further advancement of the material and also to exploit as such for commercial cultivation of hybrids. The objective of this research was to estimate the heterosis of all types i.e. mid parental heterosis, heterobeltoisis and standard heterosis for fibre quality parameters. Nine genotypes and 20 F1 hybrids derived by crossing the parental genotypes in L × T design were sown in randomized complete block design along with standard check Suvin. It was observed that the line × tester interactions made greater contribution to the total variance for all the fibre quality traits studied. Proportional contribution of lines to total variance was very low for all the traits, while testers also followed similar pattern and contributed a minimum to the total variance. However, maximum variance was extended by line × tester interaction for all the fibre quality traits studied. Out of evaluated 20 hybrids, the cross combinations namely, TCH1716 × GJHV 516, BGDS1033 × HYPS152 and TCH1716 × HYPS152 were found to be promising for Upper half mean length mean length of the fibre as they showed highest mean performance and significant positive heterosis. Further, the hybrid F2423 × HYPS152 was found to be more fine fibre and showed highest heterosis. However, the most promising hybrids for strength were TCH1716 × L766 and TCH1716 × HYPS152, while the highest heterotic effect elongation per cent was shown by TCH1716 × GJHV516. It indicated larger scope for heterosis breeding for commercial exploitation of heterosis. These promising cross combinations showing desirable heterosis over standard check can be advanced for isolation for further exploitation to improve fibre quality traits.

Keywords: Cotton; Heterosis; Heterobeltoisis; Standard heterosis; Fibre quality traits

INTRODUCTION

Cotton (*Gossypium* spp.) popularly called “White Gold” is the most important renewable natural fibre crop of global importance. World cotton production is estimated at 118.93 million bales of 480 lb (AICCIP Annual Report, 2018-19). India is maintaining the position of leading cotton growers in the world, China leading in terms of cotton production. Although cotton is cultivated in 77 countries; the five countries-China, India, United States, Brazil and Pakistan, produces 78% of the total world production from 72% of the world gross cotton area. China and Bangladesh are being the largest net importers of cotton (19% each) of the total world import, followed by Vietnam (17%), Indonesia (8%) and Pakistan (7%). The United States maintaining leading exporter of cotton (36%) of the total

world export, followed by Brazil (14%), India (10%) and Australia (9%). And the productivity front Australia leading with yield of 1814 kg/ha, followed by China (1726) and Brazil (1636) and India way behind at 507 kg lint/ha (AICCIP Annual Report, 2018-19).

Development of new variety with high yield and fibre quality is the primary objective of all cotton breeders. Heterosis breeding is an important genetic tool to facilitate yield enhancement and help to enrich many other desirable quantitative and qualitative traits in crops. Heterosis or hybrid vigour is the increment in performance of a hybrid (F1 generation) in relation to parental average and can assume positive or negative values. Exploitation of heterosis as hybrids and systematic varietal improvement through hybridization are the main tools to increase the cotton

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production in India. It is an often cross pollinated crop and amenable for both heterosis breeding as well as hybridization followed by selection in subsequent generations. The phenomenon of heterosis has proven to be the most important genetic tool in boosting the yield of self as well as cross pollinated crops and is considered as the most important breakthrough in the field of crop improvement. The exploitation of hybrid vigour in cotton on commercial scale has become feasible and economical due to easy hand emasculation and pollination. The identification of specific parental combinations capable of producing the desired level of F1 heterotic effect is important in improving the yield potential of this crop [1]. Line × Tester analysis provides a systematic approach for the detection of appropriate parents and crosses in terms of investigated traits. This method was applied to improve self and cross-pollinated plants [2]. Hence, the present study was undertaken with an aim to identify high heterotic cross combinations for fibre quality traits.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study of estimation of heterosis of *G. hirsutum* L. genotypes and F1 hybrids of cotton was carried out at RARS, Lam, Guntur, and ANGRAU during 2017-18 and 2018-19. Out of nine genotypes chosen for the study, four were designated as lines (Females) and five as testers (Males). Crosses were effected in a line x tester (4 × 5) design to produce 20 hybrid combinations. Hybridization was carried out following hand emasculation and pollination method. Crossing was taken up one week after flower initiation. Flower buds, likely to open the next day were chosen for emasculation and anthers of selected buds were removed gently with the help of nail and covered with red colored straw tube to prevent natural out crossing. Emasculation was carried out between 3 and 6 PM.

The emasculated buds were pollinated on next day with pollen of male parent between 9 and 11 AM. Four to five flower buds of female parent were pollinated by one flower of male parent. After pollination, the staminal column was covered with white colored straw tube for prevention of cross pollination with undesirable pollen. A label with details of the cross was also tied on the pedicel for identification at harvest. The white colored straw tubes were removed after completion of fertilization i.e., four days after pollination. Sufficient care was taken to ensure nicking of parents and all recommended practices were adopted to obtain sufficient number of crossed bolls for each cross combination.

During 2018-19, the nine parents and 20 hybrids and standard check (Suvini) were sown in four rows measuring six meters in a RCB design with two replications along with parents and standard hybrid check RCH 659. The row and plant spacings adopted were 105 and 60 cm, respectively. Recommended cultural practices were carried out and the crop was grown under uniform field condition to minimize environmental variations to the maximum possible extent. The data were recorded from 10 plants/entry/replication for the traits viz., Upper Half Mean Length (mm) (UHML), Mean Length (ML) (mm), fibre Uniformity Index (%) (UI), micronaire value (g/inch) and fibre strength (g/tex). Forty well developed open bolls

were randomly hand harvested from each row of parents and F1's. The bulked bolls from each genotype were ginned. The L × T analysis of heterosis was performed as suggested by [3]. Heterosis was calculated in terms of percent increase (+) or decrease (-) of the F1 hybrids against its mid parent, better parent and standard parent value as suggested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Significant differences were detected among parents and F1 hybrids for fibre quality traits studied indicating the presence of sufficient genetic variability among them (Table 1). The proportional contributions of lines and testers and their interactions (Line × Tester) to the total variance were varied among the investigated characters. Results revealed that line × tester interactions made greater contribution to the total variance for all the fibre quality traits studied. Proportional contribution of lines to total variance was very low for all the traits, while testers also followed similar pattern and contributed a minimum to the total variance. However, maximum variance was extended by line × tester interaction for all the traits studied (Table 2).

Sour ce of varia tion	DF	DF F	PH (cm)	No. of mon opods	No. of Sym podi a	No. of Bolls / Plan t	Boll wt (g)	Lint Inde x (g)	Seed inde x (g)
Repli catio ns	1	0.27	177.2 5	0.12	2.16	0.01	0.62	0.3	0.58
Treat ments	2.8	9.59	779. 66	0.51	7.04	135. 73	0.36	0.87	1.43
Par ents	8	7.37	153. 68	0.59	0.66	54.0 5	0.23	0.92	0.41
Par ents vs. Cros ses	1	13.0 4	2568 .37	0.06	6.02	188. 73	1.98	1.02	1.12
Cros ses	19	10.3 4	949. 09	0.5	9.78	167.3 4	0.32	0.84	1.87
Lines	3	27.75	1044 .9	0.44	14.13	213.7 7	0.57	0.19	3.64
Teste rs	4	8.27	1017. 64	0.48 8	13.3	275. 3	0.37	0.73	0.57
Lines x Teste rs	12	6.67	902. 27	0.52 7	7.51	119.7 4	0.24	1.04	1.86
Error	28	1.88	251.4	0.05 6	1.75	35.2 1	0.1	0.27	0.82

Total	57	5.64	509.6	0.28	4.36	83.97	0.24	0.56	1.11
σ^2 GCA		1.79	86.65	0.045	1.329	23.25	0.041	0.057	0.143
σ^2 SCA		2.39	325.4	0.235	2.881	42.26	0.07	0.021	0.52
σ^2 GCA / σ^2 SCA		0.749	0.266	0.1914	0.4619	0.552	0.5871	0.275	0.295

Table 1: Analysis of variance (mean squares) for combining ability for yield, yield components.

Source of variation	GOT (%)	SCY (Kg/ha)	Lint yield (Kg/ha)	UH ML (mm)	ML (mm)	UI (%)	Mic (ug/inch)	Bundle strength (g tex)	E (%)
Repliation	8.55	4027.3	7473.2	10.09	20.52	1196.36	0.00017	18.77	7.96
Treatments	10.2	226740.9	40968.2	8.83	8.91	912.95	0.206	7.2	0.32
Parents	12.3	150653.2	33041.9	12.99	13.5	2.12	0.278	6.17	0.13
Parents vs. Crosses	37.56	1100797	254300.1	11.88	20.22	25511.72	0.42	3.93	0.98
Crosses	7.89	212774.9	33077.6	6.92	6.39	1.78	0.16	7.8	0.36
Lines	12.37	455755.3	28916.4	11.46	9.99	1.73	0.21	11.42	0.53
Tests	13.2	132348.5	3769.57	8.42	7.7	1.75	0.28	14.56	0.43
Lines x Tests	5	178838.6	32580	5.29	5.05	1.81	0.11	4.65	0.3
Error	4.16	63765.36	10931.2	2.57	1.16	944.56	0.03	3.66	0.83
Total	7.22	142775.5	25625.6	5.78	5.31	1122.35	0.119	5.67	0.71
σ^2 GCA	0.959	25587.3	2485.8	0.8188	0.853	-104.75	0.0239	1.036	-0.038

σ^2 SCA	0.4196.6	57534.3	10824.3	1.359	1.942	-471.4	0.037	0.492	-0.264
σ^2 GCA / σ^2 SCA	2.289	0.448	0.0079	0.6025	0.439	-0.2222	0.6128	0.021	-0.1445

Table 2: Analysis of variance (mean squares) yield components and quality parameters in cotton.

Upper half mean length (mm)

Estimation of heterotic effects is necessary to identify the new cross combinations that are suitable for direct exploitation. Presence of sizeable magnitude of heterosis is very crucial for its exploitation in crop improvement programme. Amount of heterosis in F1 is indication of genetic diversity among the parents involved in crosses [4]. Heterosis breeding has led to considerable yield improvements in a most of the cross as well as self-pollinated crops. Estimation of heterosis guides the breeder to identify the superior crosses that are likely to throw transgressive segregants [5]. The directions and magnitude of heterosis and type of gene action determines the further scope of exploitation. The measures of heterosis over better parent (heterobeltiosis) and over standard check (standard heterosis) are better rational parameters for assessing its practical utility.

Fibre fineness, uniformity, length and strength affect spinning efficiency. Fibre length is critical for textile processing and varies greatly for different cottons due to genetic differences. The fibres of long staple lengths produce smoother and stronger fabrics as cotton fibres of long staple lengths are finer, stronger and also more flexible than fibres of short staple length.

The mean performance of UHML ranged between 24.65 mm (GSHV179 x GJHV516) to 30.70 (TCH1716 x GJHV516). Out of 20 hybrids evaluated, nine hybrids manifested positive and significant heterosis over standard check and the maximum value was observed for the cross TCH1716 x GJHV516 (21.34 %) followed by BGDS 1033 x HYPS 152 (20.95%) and TCH1716 x HYPS152 (17.19%). Similarly, heterobeltiosis for UHML ranged between -20.73 (GSHV179 x L766) and 7.53 (TCH1716 x GJHV516). Out of 20 cross combinations, six hybrids showed significant negative heterosis over better parent. However, the cross combination TCH1716 x GJHV516 (11.13 %) also showed heterosis over mid parent. The results of heterosis are in conformity with the reports was shown in Table 3 [6-10].

Cross combination	UHML (mm)				ML (mm)				Mic (ug/inch)			
	Me	M	BP	SC	Me	M	B	SC	Me	M	B	SC
TCH1716 x L765	29.1	-0.68	-3.16	15.02	24.1	-1.33	3.79	17.56	4.23	-1.76	-4.76	2.56
TCH1716 x 7	30.11	11.13	7.53	21.34	25.65	12.25	7.77	25.12	3.764	-8.94	-11.93	-5.13

The mean strength of hybrids stretched between 25.20 (F2453 × GISV164) and 31.15 (TCH1716 × L766). Out of 20 hybrids, the cross combination TCH1716 × L766 expressed significant standard heterosis in positive direction for fibre strength (15.37%) followed by TCH1716 × HYPS152 (15.19%). No other hybrids could realize the positive heterosis of any kind in the present study and few of male sterility based hybrids for fibre strength, and these are conformed in the present study results [16,17].

Elongation (%)

The mean performance for elongation per cent of fibre ranged from 4.90 (BGDS1033 × GJHV516) to 6.3 % (TCH1716 × GJHV516). The estimate of heterosis for elongation per cent over standard check varied between 2.80 (BGDS1033 × GJHV516) and 31.25 per cent (TCH1716 × GJHV516). All the hybrids evaluated registered positive standard heterosis for elongation per cent. Further, it is observed that none of the hybrid could record significant superiority of heterosis of any type. However, positive heterobeltiosis was registered by 13 hybrids and 12 hybrids recorded positive heterosis over mid parent indicating that improvement in elongation of the fibre is a little. Similarly, low per cent elongation [18].

CONCLUSION

Fibre quality parameters of cotton, fibre length and fineness have a vital influence on the yarn strength. The increasing fibre length results in improved yarn strength because a long fibre generates a greater frictional resistance to an external force. High fibre length and the tensile strength of the fibres becomes the controlling factor of yarn strength. The developing high fibre length and strength cultivars or hybrids are essential to current modernized spinning mills. Therefore, the present study was carried out for improving fibre quality traits from upland cotton by line × tester design. Out of evaluated 20 hybrids, the cross combinations namely, TCH1716 × GJHV 516, BGDS1033 × HYPS152 and TCH 1716 × HYPS152 were found to be promising for Upper half mean length mean length of the fibre as they showed highest mean performance and significant positive heterosis. Further, the hybrid F2423 × HYPS152 was found to be more fine fibre and showed maximum heterosis. However, the most promising hybrids for strength were TCH 1716 × L766 and TCH1716 × HYPS152 while the highest heterotic effect elongation per cent was TCH1716 × GJHV516. It indicates larger scope for heterosis breeding for commercial exploitation of heterosis. These promising cross combinations showing desirable heterosis over standard check can be advanced for isolation for further exploitation to improve fibre quality traits.

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